

MUSICAL SONIFICATION IN ELECTRONIC THERAPY AIDS FOR MOTOR-FUNCTIONAL TREATMENT – A SMARTPHONE APPROACH

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ABSTRACT

This work presents a system which uses an *Android* smartphone to measure the wrist motion of patients in ergotherapy and creates musical sounds out of it, which can make exercises more attractive for patients. The auditory feedback is used in a bimodal context (together with visual feedback on the smartphone's display). The underlying concept is to implement a therapy aid that transports the principles of music therapy to motor-functional therapy using a classical sonification approach and to create an electronic instrument in this way. Wind chime sounds are used to sonify the patient's wrist motion, a three-dimensional parameter mapping was implemented. The system was evaluated in a qualitative pilot study with one therapist and five patients. The responses to the musical auditory feedback were different from patient to patient. Musical auditory feedback in therapy can encourage patients on one hand, on the other hand it can also be perceived disturbing or discouraging. From this observation we conclude that sound in electronic therapy aids in fields other than music therapy should be made optional. Multimodal electronic therapy aids, where sound can be toggled on and off, are possible applications.

1. INTRODUCTION

The use of electronic therapy aids in music therapy has recently gained more and more attention in research [1].

In a broader sense, music therapy can not only be applied to the treatment of psychological diseases, but also to the treatment of motor-functional impairments.

Other approaches in the treatment of such impairments are movement sonification systems. In motor-functional treatment such systems have shown to be innovative alternatives to traditional movement data monitoring systems [2, 3].

Wouldn't it be interesting to combine the field of electronic therapy aids in music therapy with the field of movement sonification in order to create an instrument-like application aiming to improve patients' physical and cognitive abilities? Fig. 1 shows how the field of research that is explored in this paper aligns between the related fields.

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Figure 1. Position of the explored field of research with respect to other fields

Mobile music apps are applications for mobile end-user devices that incorporate sound as a central element. These applications can be virtual models of acoustic or electronic instruments as well as abstract instruments, augmented reality applications and musical games. Whatever kind a mobile music instrument be, it is often a strongly simplified version of the real model that it is based on or – in the case of an abstract instrument – (viewed from a traditional-virtuoso position) a very simple instrument. This simplicity is mostly based on the limitations of the interface (small touchscreen, no other kinaesthetic elements). Such an instrument, however, creates the opportunity of leading people with no or small musical knowledge to independently making music. The “toy character”, which might be the biggest point of criticism from a traditional-virtuoso point of view, can be a great advantage for the use in a therapeutic context.

The three-dimensional accelerometer, which is nowadays integrated in all smartphones, enables the use of mobile music apps also in motor-functional therapy. Patients' movements can be sonified, which provides them an auditory feedback of their movements (possibly in addition to a visual feedback). In this way, motor-functional therapy can be more attractive and easily accessible for patients and thus encourage them to do certain exercises on their own.

We see the great potential of musical movement sonification in *mobile music apps* in therapy situations, where patients are physically as well as cognitively challenged, because both interacting with sound in a musical way and using sound as feedback address cognitive abilities. Ergotherapy (or occupational therapy) is a well suitable application.

As an application example a *mobile music* therapy aid for motor functional therapy of the wrist is developed. The

wrist is frequently treated in ergotherapy not just with orthopaedically-only impaired patients, but also with patients with neurologic impairments, in order to regain motor skills. Reestablishing motion and improving its coordination are important goals in such a therapy. These goals are pursued by repetitive and varied exercising of skills that are relevant to the respective patient's everyday life. In this connection it is an advantage if patients do exercises alone and independently.

An application such as the one described in this paper aids this form of therapy, because therapy goals are pursued in a playful way and body functions are exercised by attending an external task.

2. RELATED WORK

2.1 Electronic therapy aids in music therapy

Magee (2006) [4] describes the technical applications and constraints of electronic therapy instruments. Based on a survey the reasons for the far-reaching rejection of electronic instruments on behalf of music therapists are discussed. A lack of sufficient training possibilities for therapists was found to be the main reason of this rejection.

Magee and Burland (2008) [5] propose a treatment model for music therapy with electronic therapy aids. They name complex physical and sensory impairments, motivation problems and certain needs for self-expression as indications and cases where patients are not aware of the causal effectiveness of the treatment as contraindications for the use of electronic therapy aids.

Hadley et al. (2013) [1] give a detailed overview of both the historic context and the current situation concerning the use of music technology in music therapy.

2.2 Movement sonification

Godbout et al. (2014) [6] propose a mobile movement sonification system for athletes. They use accelerometer data from an *Armour 39* chest strap to sense the athletes motion and a sonification algorithm running on an *Android* device using *PdDroidParty* in order to provide auditory feedback to an athlete.

Vogt et al. (2009) [2] implemented a movement sonification system, where movements are sensed using an optical *VICON* motion tracking system. They use very simple mappings and metaphors in order to make their system understandable for non-specialist subjects. In physiotherapy the system can be used in order to motivate patients to do certain movements.

Pauletto and Hunt (2006) [3] present a movement sonification system for use in physiotherapy, which transfers electromyographic data to the auditory domain. A simple amplitude modulation approach was chosen for the parameter mapping. The system was evaluated in an experiment with 21 subjects. It was found that the sonification implicitly provided auditory metaphors related to nature events. The authors conclude that these metaphors contribute to the usability of the feedback tool.

3. DESIGN CRITERIA

Unlike the movement sonification systems described in section 2.2 we do not intend to use sound as an information channel in the first place in our system. Rather a musical instrument that accompanies motor-functional exercises in therapy should be created. This principal is closer to music therapy for treatment of physical inhibitions than to movement sonification in health application as it has been previously implemented. However, in order to create such a kind of instrument, we intend to use a typical parameter mapping, which is a principal coming from the field of sonification.

Since the purpose of the system is to make exercising more attractive for patients, the sound we use has to be appealing. Completely abstract sounds (such as sine tones) can not meet up with this requirement. One has to be able to create a metaphor that exalts patients' imagination. Pleasantness of the sound is also an aspect that was given weight to in the design process.

This led us to the idea of building a wind chime instrument model. In this model we intended to create several unique sounds with different characteristics that are controlled by the patient's hand position in order to make the application as intuitive as possible. Furthermore, nature metaphors should help the patient and the therapist recognize characteristic sounds. These metaphors are described in section 4.5.

4. MOTOR-FUNCTIONAL WRIST TREATMENT - SYSTEM DESCRIPTION

The system we implemented uses an *Android* smartphone, a special glove which is used to fix the smartphone to the patients hand and a special therapy arm rest to stabilize the patient's lower arm. Fig. 2 shows the additional components which are required besides the smartphone. An instrument app which provides visual and musical auditory feedback to a patient was implemented on the *Android* smartphone. For visual rendering, the *Processing* *Android* library and the *Processing* GUI library *controlP5* was used. Sound synthesis is done with *Pure Data* using the *libpd* [7] *Android* API to integrate the patch in the *Android* app. The sound is played back via the smartphone's loudspeaker.

(a) Therapy arm rest

(b) Special glove with vacuum cup to attach the smartphone to the patients hand

Figure 2. Additional system components

Figure 3. System in use

4.1 Capturing the motion

The motion of the human wrist can be described as a rotation of the hand around two axes. The palmar-dorsal movement is a flexion towards the palm of the hand (*palmar flexion*, maximum angle: 80°) respectively an extension towards the back of the hand (*dorsiflexion*, maximum angle: 60°). The radial-ulnar movement describes the moves of the hand towards the little finger (*ulnar abduction*, maximum angle: 40°) and towards the thumb (*radial abduction*, maximum angle: 20°) [8].

Movements of the patient's wrist are indirectly measured using the smartphone's accelerometer; we decided to use the following approach for the detection of the hand position: In therapy the thumb side of the hand, on which the smartphone is attached in landscape format (see Fig. 3 and 4), points towards the patient. The patient's lower arm lies on a special therapy arm rest. The angle between the arm rest and the horizontal is at least 45° .

When viewing the smartphone's rotation in nautical angles *yaw*, *pitch* and *roll*, a palmar-dorsal movement of the wrist corresponds to a *pitch* movement. A radial-ulnar movement analogously corresponds to a *roll* movement (where the roll rotation axis is the *y*-axis of the smartphone). This consideration requires, that no supination (outwards rotation) or pronation (inwards rotation) of the lower arm is performed.

Now, when assuming that no other acceleration but gravity affects the smartphone and neither the pitch nor the roll rotation axis points in the direction of the gravitation vector, the pitch and the roll angle can be calculated from the accelerometer data.

When the palmar-dorsal rotation axis is parallel to the gravitation vector (roll angle is close to $\pm 90^\circ$), palmar-dorsal movements can not be properly captured anymore. For this reason, the smartphone must never be horizontally oriented. The minimum 45° tilt of the lower arm follows from a maximum ulnar abduction of 40° and a safety buffer of 5° . Depending on the smartphone's roll angle in the initial position (arm lies on the therapy rest, no radial or ulnar movement), a calibration is executed for the calculation of the radial-ulnar wrist abduction.

The wrist position which is detected in this way is denoted as

- $PD(t)$... palmar flexion (negative values) or dorsiflexion (positive values) (range: $-60^\circ \dots 80^\circ$)
- $RU(t)$... radial abduction (negative values) or ulnar abduction (positive values) (range: $-20^\circ \dots 40^\circ$)

Figure 4. Position of the (left) lower arm when using the therapy aid; illustration of the wrist motion

Figure 5. Graphical surface of the app

4.2 Data processing and visual feedback

Fig. 5 shows the graphical surface of the app. The transparent background images in the particular quadrants of the graphical surface are explained below in section 4.5.

The range of motion of a healthy human wrist can be described as an ellipse in a coordinate system which is defined by the two motion angles (palmar-dorsal; radial-ulnar) [9]. Therefore, the maximum (healthy) range of motion is shown as a black ellipse on the graphical surface. The exercise range of motion, which can be set by the therapist, is shown as a red ellipse, which is distorted in the following way: In each half plane, the ellipse for the maximum range of motion is scaled to the maximum exercise angle set by the therapist in order to obtain the exercise range of motion (upper half plane - ulnar abduction UA_{exmax} , lower half plane - radial abduction RA_{exmax} , inner half plane - palmar flexion PF_{exmax} , outer half plane - dorsiflexion DF_{exmax}).

A green dot on the screen represents the current position of the patient's hand ($PD(t)$, $RU(t)$). An optional violet dot serves as a guiding point, as it performs movements (random movement or circular movement) and the patient should follow it with the green dot. The guiding point only moves inside the boundaries of the set exercise range of motion.

From the detected hand position, also the following quantities are calculated:

$$v_{wrist}(t) = \sqrt{\dot{P}D^2(t) + \dot{R}U^2(t)}$$

... absolute angular velocity; unit: $\left[\frac{\circ}{s} \right]$ (1)

$$a_{wrist}(t) = \dot{v}_{wrist}(t)$$

... absolute angular acceleration; unit: $\left[\frac{\circ}{s^2} \right]$ (2)

As patients should not make their movements too edgy, a_{wrist} should not become too high. We therefore implemented a multimodal warning clue, when a_{wrist} exceeds a certain value. The threshold can be manually changed. On the visual side, a short red flashing of the screen signalizes a movement being to edgy. The auditory supplement of this clue is described in section 4.3

4.3 Musical sonification

In order to create a musical sonification of the wrist motion, an instrument model of a wind chime was built. A sample of a wooden chime sound and a sample of metallic chime sound are used to create two different instances of the wind chime. The playback speed of the samples is varied in order to create different musical pitches. We use discrete pitches on a pentatonic scale. The samples were polyphonically played back, each playback instance starting at a random point of time. The density and the level of playback as well as the pitch range are parameters that can be varied to change the sound. Furthermore, the balance between the wooden instance and the metallic instance of the wind chime can be varied.

The following mappings were used for the musical sonification:

1. Angular velocity \rightarrow density, level

The more the wrist is moved, the denser and louder the sound becomes. Fig. 6 illustrates the mapping. For the computation of the time distance between two note onsets, first a probability value p is calculated from the angular velocity as

$$p = \min\left(v_{wrist} \cdot 0.017 \frac{1}{\frac{\circ}{s}}, 0.5\right). \quad (3)$$

For practical reasons, a clock with a fixed clock cycle interval of 4ms creates discrete time events. For each event, a uniform distributed random value between 0 and 1 is computed. If the value is smaller than p , a chime sample is played back, otherwise nothing is done. This results in the fact that each 4ms a chime sample is played back with the probability p . The temporal resolution of 4ms is adequate for this synthesis: The user can not tell that the events are actually triggered by a clock with a fixed cycle interval, and the CPU load is compatible. The mapping of the angular velocity v_{wrist} to the probability p is linear, using the probability factor $0.017 \frac{s}{\circ}$, which was subjectively adjusted, so the system reacts already to relatively small movements, but natural movements do not immediately lead to an extremely dense sound. Furthermore, p is clipped to 0.5 (this

is equivalent to an angular velocity of $29.4 \frac{\circ}{s}$) in order not to let the sound get too dense and to keep some randomness even with fast movements.

The time interval between two note onsets can therefore be calculated as

$$\tau_d = 4 \text{ ms} \cdot Q, \quad (4)$$

where Q is a negative binomial distributed random variable:

$$Q \sim \mathcal{NB}(1, p). \quad (5)$$

The resulting average time distances thus reach from 8 ms to ∞ .

Figure 6. Schematic representation of density and level mapping; please note that the illustrated notes and breaks are not literally notes with the respective note values, the time distance between the notes is (partially randomly) changing

The angular velocity also modifies the amplitude level. The relative level factor is calculated as

$$l = \left(v_{wrist} \cdot 0.34 \frac{1}{\frac{\circ}{s}} + R \right) dB, \quad (6)$$

where R is a uniformly distributed random variable with

$$R \sim \mathcal{U}(-20, 20) \quad (7)$$

The proportionality factor $0.34 \frac{s}{\circ}$ in this parameter mapping was also subjectively adjusted, so the level changes in conjunction with the density changes result in a consistent dynamic response.

2. Palmar/dorsal rotation \rightarrow wood/metal balance

Two instances of the wind chime were created, a wooden one and a metallic one. Depending on the palmar/dorsal rotation of the wrist, a crossfade is performed between the two instances. Therefore, the palmar/dorsal deviation is normalized according to the set exercise range of motion:

$$PD_{norm}(t) = \frac{PD(t) + PF_{ex_{max}}}{DF_{ex_{max}} + PF_{ex_{max}}} \quad (\text{range} : 0 \dots 1) \quad (8)$$

From this value, the levels of the wood and the metal chimes are calculated according to the crossfade function displayed in Fig. 7. We decided to create a rather steep crossfade in order to make changes clearly noticeable. Therefore, the amplitudes were clipped at $PD_{norm}(t) = 0.3$ resp. $PD_{norm}(t) = 0.7$. For $0.3 < PD_{norm}(t) < 0.7$, also very small changes in the palmar/dorsal rotation can thus be noticed in the sound.

Figure 7. Schematic representation of balance mapping

3. Radial/ulnar deviation → pitch

The tonal repertoire that is used by the wind chimes at one certain point of time is a four-note section from a pentatonic scale. For one particular note at this point of time, the pitch (= playback speed) is randomly selected from the four possible pitches. Choosing from four different pitches should ensure, that the resulting polyphonic chime sound is rich in variety and thus pleasant. The tonal repertoire for one point of time could not be chosen larger, because then the mapping, which is described below, would not create enough distinguishable tonal repertoires any more.

Analogously to the normalization of the palmar/dorsal rotation, the radial/ulnar rotation is normalized:

$$RU_{norm}(t) = \frac{RU(t) + RA_{ex_{max}}}{UA_{ex_{max}} + RA_{ex_{max}}} \quad (\text{range} : 0 \dots 1) \quad (9)$$

We mapped this normalized measure to the pitch of the selected section of a C-major pentatonic scale reaching from $C3$ up to $D7$. The mapping was performed in such a way, that for $RU_{norm}(t) = 0$, the lowest section of the scale was the tone repertoire ($C3, D3, E3, G3$) and for $RU_{norm}(t) = 1$, the highest section was the tone repertoire ($G6, A6, C7, D7$). Fig. 8 schematically visualizes this mapping.

Figure 8. Schematic representation of pitch mapping

The auditory supplement of the visual warning clue described in the previous section is a loud drumbeat which is played back while the screen flashes red.

4.4 Unguided / guided exercises

Different usage modes can be set. In the basic mode, the violet dot which serves as a guiding point for the patient's movements was not displayed. In this mode, the instrument character of the app is pointed out most clearly. Patients

don't have a certain exercise, therefore their main focus is on creating interesting sounds. With the guiding point visible, there exist three guiding modes. In all modes, the guiding point's speed depends on the angular distance of the patient's hand position to the guided position: When the patient's hand position is close to the guided position, the guiding point moves faster, when it is further away, it moves slower. This ensures that patients do not rush to follow the guiding point, because it is much more important, that the movements are smooth, than making them fast.

The first guiding mode is a random ribbon movement. Therefore, the palmar-dorsal and the radial-ulnar coordinates change over time as sine functions, which are asynchronous (different frequencies). The constantly changing phase shift creates a ribbon movement, that seems random.

The second guiding mode is a clockwise circular movement (circumduction). Therefore, the palmar-dorsal and the radial-ulnar coordinates change over time with synchronous sine functions, one being 90° phase shifted with respect to the other. The radius is also varied over time.

The third guiding mode is a counter-clockwise circular movement, it is created analogously to the clockwise circular movement.

The guiding point coordinates are scaled and cropped in order to remain within the set exercise range of motion.

4.5 Nature metaphors

In order to make the mapping easier to understand, metaphoric nature images are assigned to the sound characteristics. As seen in Fig. 5, photos of landscapes are transparently displayed on the screen to remind patients of the metaphors. The metaphor for high-pitched wooden sounds are raindrops, because high pitched percussive sounds with a short sustain resemble the sound of rain. Low-pitched wooden sounds resemble the sound of colliding wood blocks, therefore the metaphor for this characteristic is a forest. The metaphor for a metallic, high sounds is a glacier, high pitched metallic chime sounds can be associated to ice crystals. The metaphor for low-pitched metallic sounds is a field at an alp, because the sound resembles cowbells.

5. EVALUATION

The system was evaluated in a pilot test with one therapist and five patients. Both the therapist and the patients were asked to fill in questionnaires after using the system in therapy. The therapist was extensively informed about how to use the system both orally and written. The patients were informed about the intention of the study in written form. Written consent was acquired from both patients and therapist.

5.1 Research questions and hypotheses

With the pilot study, we aimed to find answers to the following research questions:

- *Could a system that is intuitively understandable be successfully created?*

- *How do patients and therapists estimate the role of the sound in the application?*
- *Does the system motivate patients to do more exercises?*

We hypothesized that the system is intuitive due to the multimodal feedback: Even if one (the auditory or the visual) feedback is not perceived intuitive enough and therefore would lead to confusion if presented solely, the other will compensate and help creating a comprehensible multimodal perception. Also the nature metaphors we gave the therapist and patients as an orientation help should improve the intuitiveness of the system. We did not make any hypothesis about the role of sound that the patient sees in the application, it was clear that (as in most cases with auditory display) pleasantness might be a problematic aspect. Another hypothesis was that for patients who don't perceive the sound disturbing, such a novel therapy aid would be interesting and therefore motivate them to do more exercises.

5.2 Participant demographics

Five ergotherapy patients took part in the study. The patients were aged between 57 and 83 years, four of the five subjects were female, one was male. The patients were all treated for neurological diseases. Two of the five subjects suffered from multiple sclerosis, three received treatment because they have had a cerebrovascular accident (stroke).

5.3 Conduct

The application of the therapy aid was integrated in a normal therapy session. With four of the patients the therapy session was held in a home visit, with one the therapy session was held in a practice room. The smartphone used in the evaluation was a *Samsung Galaxy S3 mini*. Before exercising with a patient, the therapist set the exercise range of motion in the app settings according to the patient's abilities.

First, the patients used the system without having the exercise of following a guiding point. They should freely try out, how sound characteristics changed, when moving the hand in different directions. The sound metaphors and the nature images on the screen were explained in order enhance this learning process. The patients were also instructed to move their hand as smoothly as possible, the warning clue was demonstrated.

When the patients had a feeling for the changes in sound they could create, the therapist set different guiding modes (random movement, clockwise circumduction, counter-clockwise circumduction). The patients were given the exercise of following the (violet) guiding point, without making movements that are too edgy.

The whole application of the therapy app took a total of approximately 20 minutes. Filling in the questionnaire took approximately 5-10 minutes.

5.4 Methods, results and discussion

First, both patients and therapist were asked about their previous experience with electronic therapy aids, their mu-

sical knowledge / experience and if they generally find the use of a smartphone in therapy sensible. Therapist and patients had no or few experience with electronic therapy aids, considered their musical knowledge rather small and – on average – found the use of a smartphone in therapy rather sensible.

The questionnaire which was used to evaluate the system featured several statements. The patients should rate on a five-point Likert scale [10], to which extent the particular statements applied to them. The Likert scale points were: *does not apply at all*, *rather does not apply*, *yes and no*, *rather applies* and *totally applies*. Furthermore, the questionnaire featured some open-ended questions, where patients should elaborate different aspects of their experiences with the system. A similar questionnaire was created for the therapist.

Most of the patients and the therapist considered the system rather intuitive. All of the patients found the statement *"I clearly understood my exercises."* totally applicable. Focusing on the exercises was also not considered a problem, patients either rated the statement *"I could focus well on the exercises."* with *rather applies* or *totally applies*. The mappings in the motion sonification (statement *"I quickly and clearly understood how my motion affected the sound."*) was considered rather intuitive by four of the five patients. The visual feedback was also perceived intuitive. These findings confirm the hypothesis we made about the intuitiveness of the system. In contrary to our hypotheses, the responses to the nature metaphor images on the screen were rather negative, 4 of the 5 patients totally disagreed to the statement *"I find the nature metaphors and the landscape images on the screen useful"*. We suppose that the negative response is due to a non-optimal integration of the images in the graphical surface. The images were too small to view them on a smartphone screen and could therefore not be identified correctly. The therapist however reported that when explaining the application to her patients, the nature metaphors were very useful and might enhance the whole sound perception. Therefore we do not reject the hypothesis that the nature metaphors improve the intuitiveness of the system. The audiovisual warning clue in case of too edgy movements was also not found to be very sensible. The agreement to the statement *"I find the drumbeat, which was played back when movements were too edgy, useful."* was pretty diverse. Two of the subjects rather disagreed, one fully disagreed, one was undecided and one rather agreed. However, the therapist fully agreed to the statement. This shows that warning clues seem to provide good feedback but - from a psychological point of view - are rather inappropriate in therapy, because they might discourage patients.

Concerning the role of the sound in the application the following results were found: The sound was considered moderately pleasant, where some patients rather found to the statement *"I perceive the sound as pleasant."* applicable and others did not. When we asked patients concerning their agreement to the the statement *"I would have preferred to exercise without sound."*, two of them fully agreed, one was undecided, one rather disagreed and one fully disagreed. When asked if they had the feeling of bumping a real wind

chime, most of the patients confirmed, that the simulation of a real wind chime worked for them. We may infer that patients' responses to the use of sound in therapy are very diverse. Some patients could profit from the multi-modality of the application, others could not.

Also concerning the research question if the system would encourage patients to do more exercises the evaluation results were pretty diverse. The patients' responses to the statement "With the app, I would exercise more by myself than I used to before." were widely spread (with a tendency that patients rather would not do more exercises than they used to before). It could be seen that patients who would have preferred to exercise without sound rather tended to not finding this statement applicable while at least some of the others were partially willing to do more exercises at home with the app. The therapist reported that the responses to this statement were also strongly correlated with the patients' basic attitude in exercising on their own: Patients that already did their exercises frequently found that the application would not help them in exercising even more.

Although we can not show that our system motivates patients to do more exercises, when asked about what they found good about the system, patients who were not disturbed by the sound, answered that they liked getting to know and learning something new in therapy.

6. CONCLUSIONS AND OUTLOOK

The evaluation of the application example for motor functional therapy of the wrist showed that the perception of the musical sonification in the electronic therapy aid was very different for individual patients. A very intuitive application could be created. This is also confirmed by the fact that all patients clearly understood their exercises and could comprehend the parameter mapping despite complex neurological impairments, no or few experience with electronic therapy aids and small musical knowledge. Nevertheless, the sound in the application was perceived disturbing instead of motivating by some patients. This indicates that sound in electronic therapy aids should be made optional in fields other than music therapy. As we did not design the sound as the main carrier of information in our application, it can theoretically also be used without sound if desired. We infer that multimodal applications such as the proposed system are a well-suitable application for musical sonification in motor-functional treatment. It needs to be said that due to the small number of subjects in the evaluation the findings are not based on any statistical significance in the results, but on trends we observed in qualitatively viewing the results.

In a new evaluation the research question if the system motivates patients to do more exercises should be divided in several aspects in order to find a differentiated answer to this research question.

Answers to the open-ended questions showed that some aspects of the implementation of the system still have to be improved: the graphical surface could be simplified by removing the (probably unnecessary) landscape pictures. Feedback about how smooth the patient's movements are should be given in a more encouraging way than in the

proposed system. Adding a game-like structure (levels, rewards, ...) with an appropriate auditory supplement (e.g. auditory icons or earcons) could also improve patients' motivation to exercise.

After improving the usability of the systems, musical sonification for movements of other joints could be implemented in a similar way. Also different instruments schemes (from which the patient/therapist can freely choose) could be added in order to create a more varying user experience.

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